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MODERN APPROACHES TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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Annotation: This thesis analyzes the role of modern approaches in improving the professional training of future teachers of technological education. It highlights the effectiveness of innovative technologies integrated into the educational process, the use of digital platforms, problem-based and project-based teaching methods. It also reveals the importance of the formation of technological competence, the development of creative and critical thinking, and professional motivational factors.

Keywords: technological education, professional training, innovative technologies, competence, digital education, methodology, problem-based teaching.

Introduction.

Today, at every level of the education system, there is an increasing need for modern, innovative thinking, well-versed in technologies and able to apply them in practice. In particular, the field of technological education is one of the relevant areas that requires keeping up with the times. Future technological education teachers are emerging as mentors who not only provide knowledge, but also shape the technical thinking of students and direct them to production processes. In the modern world, digital transformation, industrial automation, the rapid development of artificial intelligence and advanced information and communication technologies require teachers to take a new approach, constantly search and work on themselves. Therefore, the use of modern approaches in the professional training of future technological education teachers has become an urgent issue. It is possible to train high-quality personnel by introducing interactive methods, digital platforms, problem-based and project-based teaching technologies into the educational process, not limited to traditional knowledge and skills. This thesis highlights the role of such modern approaches in the training of future teachers of technological education, their role in the formation of their professional competence, and the positive results they bring to the education system. This not only increases the quality of

education, but also allows us to train young specialists who are competitive, enterprising, and technologically minded in society.

The effectiveness of scientific research depends, first of all, on the correctness of the chosen methodological foundations and the accuracy of scientific approaches. In studying the issue of developing the professional training of future teachers of technological education based on modern approaches, systematic, integrated, and competency-based approaches were identified as the main methodological direction. These approaches served not only to analyze the current situation, but also to identify effective methods that can be practically applied in improving the educational process.

During the research, pedagogical observation, experimental work, questionnaires and interviews were used. In particular, the use of interactive methods in the educational process - problem-based learning, project-based learning, gamification, reflection, STEAM approaches, etc. - was studied and their impact on the professional training of future teachers was assessed. At the same time, the advanced experiences of foreign countries, in particular, the USA, South Korea, Finland and Singapore in the field of technological education were analyzed, and the possibilities of their integration with the Uzbek education system were considered.

Also, as a theoretical basis, advanced scientific literature on modern educational philosophy, innovative pedagogy, information and communication technologies, and regulatory and legal documents in the field of education of the Republic of Uzbekistan were analyzed. When selecting methodological approaches, great attention was paid to the experience of practicing teachers, analysis of real processes carried out in technical schools and higher educational institutions.

In general, the selected methodological approaches served to develop a scientifically based solution to the problem under study, to substantiate modern and innovative views in the training of future teachers.

Discussion:

Improving the professional training of future teachers of technological education is currently considered one of the central directions of educational reforms. Research shows that organizing this process only by traditional methods cannot ensure the competitiveness of future teachers in the modern labor market. Therefore, the use of modern approaches is becoming an important factor for renewal and qualitative growth in pedagogical education.

During the discussion, it was found that interactive and innovative methods - problem-based learning, project-based approach, gamification, teaching through digital platforms - encourage students to be active, think independently, and solve practical problems. Especially at a time when the demand for pedagogical staff who have mastered modern technologies and can integrate them into the educational process is growing, such approaches not only improve the quality of the lesson, but also serve to form technological thinking in the minds of students.

The discussion also included comparative analyses with the experience of foreign countries, and examined the opportunities and limitations of the higher education system of Uzbekistan. It became clear that although significant work is being done to use modern technologies in the training of pedagogical staff, certain systematic approaches, didactic methodologies and updating of educational materials are required in this area. According to the results of the discussion, it was once again confirmed that future teachers of technological education should not be limited to theoretical knowledge, but should also develop as individuals who can apply them in practice and form professional skills in a modern environment. Therefore, one of the important tasks remains the orientation of pedagogical education towards innovations, the improvement of digital and technological literacy, and the creation of conditions for professional growth.

Conclusion.

In the 21st century, the educational process is rapidly being updated, and the requirements for pedagogical activity are increasing. This process is doubly relevant, especially for the field of technological education, since it is closely related to the foundations of modern professions, innovative production, and technical thinking. The analysis and observations conducted showed that organizing the professional training of future teachers of technological education based on modern approaches not only increases the quality of education, but also serves to form them as independent thinkers, creative and technologically-minded individuals.

Modern methods - problem-based learning, project-based approach, STEAM integration, development of skills in working with digital technologies - strengthen the professional competence of future teachers, turn them into practical specialists who can solve real-life problems. At the same time, the introduction of modern approaches to pedagogical education increases the

motivation of teachers, and the effectiveness of the educational process significantly increases.

In conclusion, the use of modern approaches in training personnel for the field of technological education is an important need and strategic direction of today. In this regard, scientifically based approaches, in-depth analysis of foreign experience, and methodologies adapted to the conditions of the local education system should be developed. Only then will we be able to prepare future teachers at the level of the requirements of a modern technological society.

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